

Thermodynamics of Copper (II)-8-Hydroxyquinoline-7 Sulphonic Acid Chelate-A Spectrophotometric Study.

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Copper(II) forms, in aqueous medium, a colourless complex with 8-hydroxyquinoline-7-sulphonic acid with a maximum absorbance at 235 mμ, and is stable in the pH range 1 to 3. The composition of the complex was found to be Cu(R)₂, where R stands for the ligand. The stability constant, as determined by two methods was found to be $\log K = 0.8 \pm 0.05$, and the free energy of formation of the complex was found to be $\Delta F^\circ = -13.5 \pm 0.04$ k-cal/mole at 25°. The enthalpy and entropy changes as calculated by Gibbs-Helmholtz equation was found to be -5.3 cal. and 63.11 e.u. respectively.

8 hydroxyquinoline-7-sulphonic acid forms metal chelates with a five membered ring. In recent communications from this laboratory¹, Banerji and coworkers have reported the preparation of 8 hydroxyquinoline-7-sulphonic acid and its colour reactions with various metal ions. The composition, structure and stability of the iron (III) chelate has also been reported². Different workers have also shown considerable interest in this compound³⁻⁹.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of cu - 8 hydroxyquinoline-7-sulphonate
 Curve 1. Reagent alone.
 Curve 2. $c = 5 \times 10^{-5}M$, $p = 1$; Curve 3. $c = 2.5 \times 10^{-5}M$, $p = 2$.
 Curve 4. $c = 6 \times 10^{-5}M$, $p = 3$; Curve 5. $c = 1.25 \times 10^{-5}M$, $p = 4$.

1. K. C. Srivastava and S. K. Banerji, *Chem. Age.*, 1967, **18**, 351.
2. K. Balachandran and S. K. Banerji, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1968, **37**, 263.
3. Tiao Hau Chang *et al.*, *J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **3**, 125.
4. Nasanen and Visitalo, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, **8**, 112.
5. A. Albert, *Biochem. J.*, 1853, **54**, 646.
6. A. Albert and A. Hampton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 506.
7. C. F. Richard *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 1033.
8. L. E. Maley and D. P. Mellor, *Austr. J. Sci. Res.*, 1949, 579A.
9. K. Lal and R. P. Agarwal, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 169.

Standard solutions of copper were prepared from $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (BDH-AR). The ligand was prepared by the methods referred to above and solutions obtained by dissolving its sodium salt. Sodium perchlorate was used to adjust the ionic strength. A Hilger UVISPEK (equipped with thermoplates), was used for absorbance measurements, and pH measurements were taken on a Beckman Model H-2, pH meter. The chelate was studied under optimum conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To find out the nature of the complex formed, Vosburgh and Cooper's method¹⁰ was used. The results indicate that only one complex is formed with a λ_{max} at 253 mm. The chelate was found to be stable in the pH range 1 to 3, and a temperature range 25–85°.

Fig. 2. Job's method of continuous variation.

Curve 1. $c = 5 \times 10^{-2}\text{M}$.

Curve 2. $c = 4 \times 10^{-5}\text{M}$.

Curve 3. $c = 2.5 \times 10^{-5}\text{M}$.

Curve 4. $c = 2 \times 10^{-5}\text{M}$.

The composition of the complex was established by three independent methods viz., Job's continuous variation¹¹, Harvey and Manning's slope ratio¹², and Yoe and Jones mole ratio¹³. All the three indicate a stable complex with a composition $\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2$, where L is 8 hydroxyquinoline-7-sulphonic acid.

The stability constant of the complex, as determined by the methods of Banerji and Dey¹⁴ and mole ratio was found to be $\log K = 9.8 \pm 0.05$, and the free energy of formation was found to be $\Delta F^\circ = -13.5$ kcal/mole at 25°.

10. W. C. Vosburgh and G. R. Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.

11. P. Job, *Ann. Chimie*, 1928, (x) **9**, 113; 1936, (xi) **6**, 97.

12. A. E. Harvey and D. L. Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4744.

13. J. H. Joe and A. L. Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.

14. S. K. Banerji and A. K. Dey, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1961, **30**, (1), 179.

The entropy and enthalpy changes as determined using temperature coefficient method and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation is represented below :

Fig. 3. Mole ratio method.
Final concentration of the reagent.
Curve 1. 5×10^{-5} M. Curve 2. 2.5×10^{-5} M.

TABLE 1

Temp.	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°
log K	9.8	9.84	9.89	9.98	10.03
ΔF°	-13.40	-13.68	-14.08	-14.25	-15.07
ΔS	62.7	62.7	63.1	62.8	64.10

The ΔH of the reaction, as calculated from the curve (I/T vs H) was found to be -5.3 , and ΔS of the reaction had a mean value $= 63.01$. The stability constants at different ionic strengths at pH 3 and temperature of 25° has been laid in table 2.

TABLE 2

Ionic strength K ($\times 10^3$)	0.02	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.5
	6.4	5.5	4.62	3.7	3.2	3.18

Fig. 4. Slope ratio method.
1-1 metal varying. 2-2 reagent varying.
Solid lines refer to 253nm and broken lines refer to 255nm.

The decrease in the stability constant with increase in the ionic strength is according to the expectations. Its becoming constant after an ionic strength 0.3, may be attributed to the fact that the activity coefficient of the ion passes through a minimum as the ionic strength increases. The chelate may be considered to be formed by the establishment of the coordinate link between the metal ion and nitrogen.

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